

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A PHYTOPHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEW ON
THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF ARECA CATECHU**Girammagari Triveni ¹, Dr. C. Girish ^{2*}^{1,2} S.V.U. College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sri Venkateshwara University,
Tirupati - 517502. A.P, India.**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Areca catechu belongs to the palm family. It is commonly known as betel nut. *Areca catechu* has capability of increasing the nervous activity in the body. *Areca* nut has several bioactivities such as Antioxidant activity, Hypoglycaemic activity, Hypolipidemic activity, Antihypertensive activity, Anti depression activity and Anticoagulant activity. The nut of this plant consists of various chemical constituents like alkaloids, tannins, arecoline, arecadine and fibres. Arecoline and Guvacoline are the different carboxylic acids isolated from the plant. In general the nut of *Areca catechu* is widely used by the people for the purpose of chewing as a habit. It may leads to addiction and it is also one of the causes of oral cancer. The Ethanolic extract of areca nut has potent antioxidant activity. *Areca* nut also has potent invitro inhibitory activity on angiotensin converting enzyme.

Keywords: *Areca catechu*, Betel nut, *Areca* nut**Corresponding author:****Dr. C. Girish,**

M.Pharm, PhD, FAGE, MABAP.

Assistant Professor,

S.V.U.College of Pharmaceutical sciences,

Sri Venkateshwara University,

Tirupati - 517502. A.P, India.

Ph No: 9290534422

E.Mail: cgirish.svu@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press G.Triveni and Dr. C. Girish, *A Phytopharmacological Review On Therapeutic Potential Of Areca Catechu.*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci.*, 2020; 07(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Plants are the important source for the investigation of new products of medicinal value for drug development. Now a several distinct chemicals derived from plants are important drugs used in one or more countries in the world. Plants have the ability to synthesize chemical compounds that help them to defend against attack from a wide variety of predators such as insects, fungi and herbivorous mammals. Those compounds are generally known as secondary metabolites and which are mainly responsible for various pharmacological activities of the plant. *Areca catechu* belongs to the genus Arecaceae and it was first described by Linnaeus [1, 2]. It is the primary source of betel nut. The betel nut raises the levels of nervous activity in the body. It is regarded as the fourth most widely used addictive substance after caffeine, nicotine and alcohol [3]. *Areca catechu* is a species of palm which grows in regions near to pacific Asia, and various parts of east Africa. The palm has primarily originated in the Philippines [4]. The frequent usage of Areca nut in India was referred in Sanskrit medical literature and also in the Hindu and Buddhist writings. The usage of betel nut, as a masticator by humans has been known since from the 4th century AD in different parts of the world. Arecanut has importance in religious, social and cultural functions in India. The betel nut is present in the ceremonial plate, as humans believe that the betel nuts having a property to increase the prosperity. The nut is offered to the guests, along with a betel leaf, as a mark of respect. In India the chewing of betel quid, which includes betel leaf, areca nut and lime, is practised at least 2,000 years old, where as the tobacco was introduced around the sixteenth century [5].

The various pharmacological investigations have stated that the Areca nut has several bioactivities such as anti-parasitic activity [6], digestive effect [7, 8], anti-depressive activity [9], anti-oxidant activity [10], anti-bacterial activity [11], anti-inflammatory and anti-analgesic activity [12]. Most of the drugs used today are simple synthetic modifications or copies of the naturally obtained Substances [13]. The present review of *Areca catechu* describes the different phyto pharmacological activities and the complete profile of the plant.

PLANT PROFILE:**Synonyms:**

The synonyms of *Areca catechu* are *Areca faufel Gaertn*, *Areca hortensis Lour*, *Areca catechu Burm.f*, *Sublimia*, *Areca comm. Ex Mart* [14]. The various common names of the plant are areca palm, areca nut palm, betel palm, Indian nut pinang palm [15].

Scientific Classification:

Kingdom	:	Plantae
Clade	:	Tracheophytes
Clade	:	Angiosperms
Clade	:	Monocots
Clade	:	Commelinids
Order	:	Arecales
Family	:	Arecaceae
Genus	:	Areca
Species	:	<i>Areca catechu</i>

Figure 1: *Areca catechu* Plant Plant Description

Areca nut is the seed or endosperm (nut) of *Areca catechu* Linn. *Areca catechu* is a slender, single-trunked and monoecious palm with a prominent crown shaft. According to old Indian scripts, such as Bhavamista (13th century) and Vagbhata (4th century), betel nut has been described as a therapeutic agent for the treatment of leukoderma, leprosy, anaemia and obesity. It is also has deworming properties and hence used as vermifuge.

The habit of Areca species is different from undergrowth palm lets to moderately robust tree palms and from solitary to clustering [16, 17]. All species in East Malaysia are solitary, except for *Areca vestiaria* but some populations of *Areca vestiaria* are single stemmed. Two Areca species in the region have stilt roots, namely *Areca novohibernica* and *Areca vestiaria*. The stilt roots are related to swampy habitats, light environments or stabilization in rocky habitats. These roots are essential for getting mechanical support and vascular function [18, 19]. Areca nut palm (*Areca catechu* L.) is cultivated mainly for its highly valuable kernel, which was obtained from the fruit. The fruit is chewed in its tender, ripe or processed form.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

The major chemical constituents of *Areca catechu* are polyphenolic compounds, alkaloids, tannin, arecoline, arecaine and fibres [20, 21]. Arecoline and Guvacoline are the different carboxylic acids isolated from the plant [22]. Caine is the active principle of the Areca nut. Aqueous extract of the betel nut contains, catechu, 15 % of tannin, gallic acid, 14% of fat, gum and alkaloids, namely 0.07% of Arecoline, 1% of Arecaine, arecaine and guvacoline. Guvacine and choline occur in traces only. All these alkaloids are chemically related to each other. Arecoline is colourless volatile and resembling nicotine [23].

USES:

In Some Asian countries such as china, Philippines, Malaysia, Myanmar, Taiwan, Vietnam and India the Areca nut is popularly used for regular chewing. Chewing areca nut is popular among working classes in Taiwan. The nut induces addiction and is the major cause of oral cancer [24]. Areca nuts in Taiwan will usually contain artificial additives like limestone powder [25].

The areca palm is also used as an interior landscaping species. It is frequently used in large indoor areas such as malls and hotels. In India the dry, fallen leaves of the plant are collected and hot-pressed into disposable palm leaf plates and bowls [26].

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIONS:**Antioxidant activity:**

The Ethanolic extract of areca nut shown to have the characteristic and potent anti-oxidant, free radical scavenging and Anti-hyaluronidase activity. But the Antioxidative effect of the seed extract was lower than the butylated hydroxy toluene, and as same as the tocopherol and was higher than ascorbic acid [27].

Hypoglycaemic Activity:

It was investigated and reported that arecoline have hypoglycaemic activity in an animal model of diabetes upon subcutaneous administration. In alloxanized rabbits (140 mg/kg), the subcutaneous administration of alkaloid fraction of *Areca catechu* (0.05 to 0.5 mg/kg) shows significant hypoglycaemic effect lasting for 4 to 6 hours [28]. But it was also observed that chronic usage of the nut is associated with higher risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus and metabolic syndrome, which was determined by a epidemiologic survey in Taiwan [29, 30].

Hypolipidemic activity:

The extract of *Areca* also identified to exhibit a strong inhibitory activity on cholesterol absorption in high cholesterol fed rats. In another study, a diet

containing corn oil with areca nut extract supplement are fed to the rats effectively lowered the absorption of triglyceride and the plasma lipid concentration [31].

It has been found that areca nut extracts exhibit in-vitro strong inhibitory activities against pancreatic cholesterol esterase (PCEase) and also found to lower the absorption of dietary cholesterol ester [32]. Furthermore, both absorption of intestinal free cholesterol and small intestinal PCEase activity were significantly lowered when fed with a diet containing free cholesterol with areca nut extract supplement [33].

Antihypertensive activity:

Areca nut reported to have potent in vitro inhibitory activity on angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE). Intravenous administration of areca nut fraction to SHR produced a rapid and marked reduction in blood pressure at doses of 10 and 15 mg/kg. The maximum antihypertensive effect of areca nut fraction at an I.V. dose of 15 mg/kg, was about 5 times as large as that of captopril at the same dose [34].

Antidepressant Activity:

The areca nut fraction potentially inhibits monoamine oxidase-A activity and thus restores or increases bioavailability of monoamines, 5-hydroxytryptamine or noradrenaline in the brain. Additional to this, forced swimming and tail-suspension tests supported that the dichloromethane fraction has antidepressant activity [35].

Anticonvulsant Activity:

Arecaine and guvacine inhibits the uptake of GABA and alpha-alanine. Large doses of arecaine (1 g/kg subcutaneous) marginally reduces the lethal effects of bicuculline in mice but appeared to have little or no anticonvulsant activity [36].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Areca catechu raise the levels of nervous activity in the body regarded as the fourth most widely used addictive substance after caffeine, nicotine and alcohol. Modern pharmacological investigations have commutated that areca nut possesses, several bioactivities such as anti-parasitic effect, digestive effect, anti-depressive effect, anti-oxidant effect, anti-bacterial effect, anti-inflammatory and anti-analgesic effects. Aqueous extract of areca nut contain catechu, tannin 15%, gallic acid, oily matter (fat 14%), gum and alkaloids like Arecoline 0.07%, Arecaine 1%, arecaine and guvacoline, guvacine and choline occur in trace only.

The extract of Areca catechu may be addictive. Ethanolic extract of areca nut have the following activities like anti-oxidative, free radical scavenging and Anti-hyaluronidase activity. It was investigated and reported that arecoline have hypoglycaemic activity in an animal model of diabetes upon subcutaneous administration. Areca extracts are also identified to exhibit a strong inhibitory activity on cholesterol absorption in high cholesterol fed rats. Areca nut fraction reported to have potent in vitro inhibitory activity on angiotensin-converting enzyme.

REFERENCES:

1. Moore HE Jr, Dransfield J. Typification of Linnean palms. *Taxon*, 1979; 28: 59-70.
2. Dransfield J, Uhl NW, Asmussen CB, Baker WJ, Harley MM, Lewis CE. *Genera Palmarum: the evolution and classification of palms*. Kew: Royal Botanic Gardens, International Palm Society and L. H. Bailey Hortorium. 2008.
3. Norton SA. Betel: consumption and consequences. *Journal of American Academy of Dermatology*, 1998; 38: 81- 88.
4. Germplasm Resources Information Network, Agricultural research service, united states Department of Agriculture. Retrieved 2008-03-02.
5. Dransfield J, Uhl NW, Asmussen CB, Baker WJ, Harley MM, Lewis CE. A new phylogenetic classification of the palm family, *Areaceae*. 2005. *Kew Bulletin* 60: 559-569.
6. Tian XF, Dai JJ, Dong L, He BL, Yang ZY, Zhao LN. Ultra-structure observation on *Taenia Solium* Experlled by decoction of Areca and Pumpkin seeds. *Chin J Para Dis Con*, 1998; 15: 363-364.
7. Li C, Fan YF, Lv T, Wei MX, Hu B. Study on extraction separation of Areca catechu and the effect on gastric smooth muscle contraction on rats. *China J Chin Med*, 2013; 28: 683-685.
8. Guo XJ. Effect of areca nut on gastrointestinal motility and neurotransmitters in rats. *Chin J Integ Trad West Med Dig*, 2008; 17: 300-303.
9. Dar A, Khatoon S. Behavioral and biochemical studies of dichloromethane fraction from the Areca catechu nut. *Pharmacol Biochem Behav*, 2000; 65: 1-6.
10. Bhandare AM, Kshirsagar AD, Vyawahare NS, Hadambar AA, Thorve VS. Potential analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of hydroalcoholic extract of Areca catechu L. nut. *Food Che. Toxicol*, 2010; 48: 3412-3417.
11. Boniface P, Verma SK, Cheema HS, Daroka MP, Pal A. Evaluation of antimalarial and antimicrobial activities of extract and fractions from Areca catechu (Abstract). *Int J Infect Dis*, 2014; 21: 228-229.
12. Khan S, Mehmood MH, Ali AN, Ahmed FS, Dar A, Gilani AH. Studies on anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities of betel nut in rodents. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2011; 135: 654-661.
13. Mulabagal Vanisree, Chen-Yue, Lee, Shu-Fung Lo, Satish Manohar Nalawade, Chien Yih Lin, Hsin-Sheng Tsay: Studies on the production of some important secondary metabolites from medicinal plants by plant tissue cultures. *Bot. Bull. Acad. Sin*, 2004; 45:1-2.
14. Kew World checklist of selected plant Families. 2006; 25-32.
15. Simon Gardener, Pindar sidisunthorn and lai Ee May, 2011. *Heritage Trees of Penang*. Penang: areca Books.
16. Dransfield J. 1984. The genus *Areca* (Palmae: Arecoideae) in Borneo. *Kew Bulletin* 39: 1-22.
17. Uhl NW, Dransfield J. 1987. *Genera palmarum*. Lawrence, KS: Allen Press.
18. Frangi JL, Ponce MM. 1985. The root system of *Prestoea Montana* and its ecological significance. *Principes* 29: 13-19
19. Tomlinson PB. 1990. *The structural biology of palms*. Oxford: Clarendon Press
20. IARC Working Group, Tobacco habits other than smoking; betel quid and areca-nut chewing; and some related nitrosamines. Lyon, France, 23-30, 1984. *IARC Monogr Eval Carcinog Risk Chem Hum*, 37, 1985, 1-268
21. Wang CK, Su HY, Lii CK, Chemical composition and toxicity of Taiwanese betel quid extract. *Food Chem Toxicol*, 1999; 37: 135- 44.
22. Chin-Kun Wang, Wen-Hsiu Lee, and Chin-Hui Peng, Contents of Phenolics and Alkaloids in Areca Catechu Linn. During Maturation. *J. Agric. Food Chem*. 1997; 45 (4): 1185-1188.
23. Thomas and Maxlennan. Slaked lime and betel cancer in Papua New Guinea. *The Lancet*, 1992; 340(8819): 577- 578.
24. Hemantha Amarasinghe. Betelquid chewing with or without tobacco is a major risk factor for oral potentially malignant disorders in Sri Lanka. *Oral Oncology*, 2010; 46(4): 297- 301.
25. Palm leaf plates Archived; 2016; At the Wayback Machine on the website the whole Leafco.com.
26. Dr. Nadkarni K.M., *Indian material Medica*, 1976; 3rd Ed, Vol. 1, Bombay Popular Prakashan, Mumbai, Page no. 130-133.
27. BJ Kim, JH Kim, HP Kim and MY Heo: Biological screening of 100 plant extracts for cosmetic use (II): Anti-oxidative activity and free radical scavenging activity. *Int JCosmetic Sci*, 1997; 19: 299- 307.
28. Chempakam B., Hypoglycaemic activity of arecoline in betel nut *Areca catechu L.*, *Ind. J of Exp. Biol*, 1993; 31(5): 474- 475.

29. Tung TH, Chiu YH, Chen LS et al, Keelung Community-based Integrated Screening programme No. 2. A population-based study of the association between areca nut chewing and type 2 diabetes mellitus in men (Keelung Community-based Integrated Screening programme No. 2), *Diabetologia*, 2004; 47: 1776–1781.
30. Chung FM, Chang DM, Chen MP et al. Areca Nut Chewing is associated with metabolic syndrome. Role of tumour necrosis factor, leptin, and white blood cell count in betel nut chewing-related metabolic derangements, *Diabetes Care*, 2006; 29: 14- 17.
31. Byun SJ, Kim HS, Jeon SM, Park YB and MS Choi: Supplementation of Areca catechu L. extract alters triglyceride absorption and cholesterol metabolism in rats. *Ann Nutr Metab*, 2001; 45(6):279-284.
32. SM Jeon, HS Kim, TG Lee, SH Ryu, PG Suh, SJ Byun YB, Park, MS Choi: Lower absorption of cholesteryl oleate in rats supplemented with Areca catechu L. extract. *Ann Nutr Metab*, 2000; 44(4): 170-176.
33. YB Park, SM Jeon, SJ Byun, HS Kim and MS Choi: Absorption of intestinal free cholesterol is lowered by supplementation of Areca catechu L. extract in rats. *Life Sci*. 2002; 70(16):1849- 1859
34. J Inokuchi, H Okabe, T Yamauchi, A Nagamatsu, G Nonaka, I Nishioka: Antihypertensive substance in seeds of Areca catechu L. *Life Sci* 1986; 38(15): 1375-1382.
35. Dar and S. Khatoon, Behavioral and biochemical studies of dichloromethane fraction from Areca catechu nut, *Pharmacology, Biochemistry and Behaviour*, 2000; 65(1): 1- 6.
36. D. Lodge, Johnston G.A.R., Curtis D.R., Brand S.J., Effects of the Areca nut constituent's areca dine and guvacine on the action of GABA in the cat central nervous system, *Brain Research*, 1977; 136 (3): 513- 522.